

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) chromosome 6D harbours the broad spectrum common bunt resistance gene *Bt11*

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(a) LOD-profiles in MP-PR1

Lunzer, M., Buerstmayr, M., Grausgruber, H., Müllner, A.E., Fallbacher, I. and Buerstmayr, H. Theoretical and Applied Genetics.

(b) LOD-profiles in MP-PR2

MP-PL 2019

MP-PL 2020

MP-PL BLUES across years

(c) LOD-profiles in MP-PL

(d) LOD-profiles in MP-MM

Supplementary File 6: LOD profiles based on model selection results from the *stepwise*-function in R package *r/qtl* (Broman et al., 2003). Positions of LOD-peaks are indicated in centi Morgan (cM). LOD-profiles are shown for common bunt incidence scores in each individual experiment and BLUEs across experiments for each mapping populations (MP) separately: (a) MP-PR1 = PI166910 × 'Rainer' × PI166910 (c) MP-PR2 = 'Rainer' × PI166910 (d) MP-MM = M822123 × 'Mulan' (d) MP-MM = M822123 × 'Mulan'